

MAIN FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM TOURISTIC RESOURCES OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article talks about the main factors in the development of tourism, the fact that tourism is a highly profitable industry for the country, and the specific features of management in the field of tourism.*

Keywords: *management, prospective networks, international tourism, sanatorium-resort organizations, tourist resources, tourism industry*

Introduction. We all know that tourism is a highly profitable industry for the country. Tourism refers to the movement of people from one place to another, both within and outside the country. Today, tourism is becoming an integral part of the economy, providing employment to the population through the development of tourism, making their living conditions more profitable, greatly contributes to the comprehensive development of the country's economy. As a confirmation of our opinion, we can see the experience of foreign countries where the field of tourism has developed.

The role of management in the development of the tourism industry is incomparable. Our country has great potential in the field of tourism. It is for this reason that students in this field need to acquire knowledge and skills of professional training of young people, specific features of management in the field of tourism, management methods. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, stated in his address to the Oliy Majlis, "Tourism is one of the promising sectors that bring high income to the national economy today." Uzbekistan is a country with great potential in the field of tourism. There are more than 7,300 objects of cultural heritage in our country, and most of them are included in the UNESCO list. At the same time, it is possible to open new tourist destinations using the opportunities of the unique nature of our country and beautiful recreation areas. Actively involving world brands in this field, we need to pay special attention to the development of pilgrimage tourism, ecological, educational, ethnographic, gastronomic tourism and other branches of this field. In this regard, we should take into account that the use of public-private partnerships opens wide opportunities for the development of the sector.

A number of activities are being carried out by our state for the further development of the tourism sector. Expansion of the field of services for domestic and foreign tourists and increase in their quality, benefits and facilities for tourists have changed significantly over the last 2-3 years. In order to improve the quality of tourist services, a number of legal documents have been developed by the government in a new version and additions have been made. The main goal of this is to increase the flow of tourists to the country, to increase the income of the population in the country, at the same time to further develop the economy, to expand the investment attractiveness of the country, and to implement new investment projects. For this, it is necessary to train young personnel who can meet the demands of the times, who are able to meet the demands of the time, who have the potential to manage the international tourism industry in the future, and who can effectively manage tourist enterprises and properly organize and deliver services.

Main Part. The formation and development of tourism depends on the potential of tourist resources. The more diverse tourist resources the country has, the easier it is to develop tourism.

It should be noted that our country has a huge tourist resource for the development of the tourism industry. Such an opportunity exists in a few countries of the world. Beautiful nature, diverse climate, glorious history, cultural monuments, unique traditions of the regions are all embodied in our country. Tourism is a rapidly developing service industry sector of our country's economy, and the services provided in it are consumed by tourists going to the regions where the resources are available. Tourism, as a labor-intensive sector, creates many jobs not only in tourism, but also in industry, agriculture, which produces various products and goods consumed by travelers, as well as in the transport and infrastructure sectors that serve them. To create, as well as to increase the foreign currency income of the country, and on this basis, it creates an opportunity to significantly expand economic activity. About 7,300 historical cultural objects have been identified on the territory of Uzbekistan, there are several nature reserves and national parks, and there are more than 300 healing underground mineral water sources. Among the tourist resources available in our country, the place of cultural centers is of special importance. Currently, there are about 50 theaters, more than 110 museums, 2 zoos, 1 botanical garden, 1 circus, about 3000 libraries, about 170 cultural and recreational parks, and more than 50 concert halls operating in our country. There are more than 160 sanatorium-resort organizations in our country today. Most of them are located in Fergana, Tashkent and Namangan regions. Also, more than 250 recreation centers are operating, almost half of them, more than one hundred, are located in Tashkent region.

Distribution of tourist flow in 2018 by months

Conclusion

Analyzing the above statistical data of 2018, August (584,434) in our country corresponds to the lowest number of tourists in January (266,194). In general, the only touristic place of our country consists of a unique desert (desert), valleys and oases of the irrigated plain zone, and mountain landscapes, which are inextricably linked and at the same time very different from each other. They serve as a strong natural basis for establishing tourism centers and centers of various directions. It should be noted that there are very favorable conditions and opportunities in our country for ecological tourism, which is rapidly developing as an innovative direction in international tourism.

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